

Original Research Article

Stress management and employee performance: use of psychotherapy as mitigation in selected schools (School of business and economics & Health sciences) in Kisii University, Kenya

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Abstract

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Much of the work requires the employee to be on their feet and employer, colleagues and student interactions can be stressful, as employees can be verbally abused for service problems that are completely out of their control. This may result to a variety of stressors which can lead to low morale, ill health, conflicts among others. The purpose of this study is to investigate stress management and employee performance by use of psychotherapy as mitigation. Survey research design was used for this study. Purposive sampling, convenient sampling and census sampling was employed in this study. Both descriptive statistics and inferential were used to analyse data. Causes of stress positively correlated to the employee's performance $r = .429$, $P < .01$. The results indicated that work related stress positively correlated to the employee's performance $r = .429$, $P < .01$. Stress coping strategies positively correlated to the employee's performance $r = .634$, $P < .01$ level of significance. Work related stress, causes of stress and stress coping strategies have effect on employee performance. There need for university management to identify suitable stress coping strategies to help reduce stress employee work place stress.

Keywords: Stress, stressors, stress management, employee performance, psychotherapy, coping strategies, mitigation

INTRODUCTION

Job stress is increasing globally in all countries, organizations, professions, and among employees, employers, families and society in general. Studies show that employees in the United States and other developed countries experienced job stress as a serious issue hence American businesses pay more than \$150 billion annually for occupational stress which leads to the absenteeism of employees, loss productivity and low performance (Spector et al., 2002). Occupational stress has been known as a serious health issue for organizations and employees. Thus, the stressful situations of the workplace due to occupational stress lead to negative consequences like anxiety, headache,

stomach distress and cardiovascular disease (Spector et al., 2002). Hence there is need to identify how consequences of stress affect employee performance at the work place.

Much of the work requires the employee to be on their feet and employer, colleagues and student interactions can be stressful, as employees can be verbally abused for service problems that are none of their doing and completely out of their control. In addition many of them have problems in maintaining a work life balance. This may result to a variety of stressors which can lead to low morale, ill health, conflicts and high level of stress. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the

role of psychotherapy in stress management. When the occupational stress occurs, it will directly affect the performance of worker and managers of the organization. Mostly, the occupational stress comes from the job that they do. Many people not aware of occupational stress, that occurs in the organization and don't care about the occupational stress. They assume that the occupational stress will only affect their performance of work but also affect their health like heart attack, migraine that can lead to death. If people are aware about job stress, it will become worst such as suicide (Yahaya, 2010). Occupational stress is an increasingly important occupational health problem. However it may also cause subtle manifestation of morbidity that can affect personal well-being and productivity (Jayashree, 2010). Several studies have shown that occupational stress can lead to various negative consequences for the individual and the workplace (Oginska-Bulik, 2006).

Researchers cannot agree on a single definition for stress due to its complex nature (Salami et al., 2010). Stress usually defines as the reaction of individuals to demands (stressors) imposed upon them (Erkutlu & Chafra, 2006). Stress is the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker (Maxwell, 2004). Robbins (2001) defines stress as a dynamic condition in which the individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraint, or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be both uncertain and important.

In general, Job stress can be defined as the physical and emotional responses that happen when the employee's capabilities and resources cannot be coped with the demands and requirements of their job (Alves, 2005; Bianchi, 2004; Lindholm, 2006; Nakasis & Ouzouni, 2008). A phenomenon that is related to work and is known as occupational Stress may be expressed differently, and affects on employees in the different work contexts. Studying about job stress will demonstrate the perception of job stress and its negative effects on employee's satisfaction, commitment and productivity in the different contexts and situations (Michael, 2009). According to Owen (2006), stressful situations in the workplace make occupational stress which leads to negative and harmful effects on both employers and employees. So, occupational stress will have unwelcome results such as absenteeism, loss of productivity and health care resources (Abualrub and Alzaru, 2008; Nakasis and Ouzouni, 2008).

All in all, work-related stress is a growing problem that results in substantial costs to individual employees and work organizations around the globe (Hart & Cooper, 2001). Work-related stress can also impact employee productivity through increased absenteeism; imposing a direct economic cost on employers (Australian Safety and Compensation Council, 2008), voluntary turnover in the organizations (Zhang and Lee, 2011), and burnout

(Salami, 2002). In addition, there are many sources of work-related stress in organization such as new technology (Rahmani, 2009), unfair evaluation, lack of job security, unpleasant colleague, lack of managers' support, high workload, procrastination and so on.

Nowadays, many organizations, institutions and employees are experiencing the effects of stress on work performance. The effects and perception of stress vary from one person to another. What is perceived as positive stress by one person may be perceived as negative stress by another, since everyone perceives situations differently. According to Barden (2001), negative stress is becoming a major illness in the work environment, and it can debilitate employees and be costly to employers. Managers need to identify those suffering from negative stress and implement programs as a defense against stress. These programs may reduce the impact stress has on employees' work performance.

Job stress is a phenomenon that every employee or employer faces at job and handles it differently according to own way. It is basically a mismatch between the individual capabilities and organizational demand (Pediwal, 2011; Jayashree, 2010). Job stress is an unpleasant emotional situation that an individual experiences when the requirements of job are not counter balanced with his ability to cope the situation. It is a well-known phenomenon that expresses itself different in different work situations and affects the workers differently (Malek, 2010; Medi bank Private Inc., 2008). An individual experiences dysfunction in organizations expectation and his own needs due to stress. It is now becoming the global issue which is affecting all the countries, all categories of employees and societies (Haider & Supriya, 2007). The stress begins with the demand and opportunity from environment for a person and ends with the individual's response to that demand and opportunity (Shah, 2003). Hence there is need for this study to explore how stress coping strategies affect employee performance at the work place and identify suitable strategies of coping with different workplace stressors.

It is obvious that such employees have low morale, low motivation and very low job satisfaction. It seems that changes in behavior due to mental pressure would impact on both intra-organizational productivity and inter-organizational lifestyle (Gaving, 2007). Also, a common issue among the members of such professions as teachers, university professors, HR experts and social workers is burnout. When someone endures extra mental pressure and the resources to mitigate such pressure are too low, such feeling is shaped (Ivie, Garland, 2001). Therefore there is need to investigate into the impacts of stress on employee performance and use of psychotherapy in stress management. Workplace stress is a serious health and safety hazard that can have devastating effects. Stress can lead to psychosocial illnesses, such as anxiety and stress depression. Stress

can also contribute directly to physical illness; for example, tense muscles can worsen ergonomic injuries. Stress makes workers more susceptible to hazards, injury and disease. While it is true that there are sources of stress other than the workplace, this does not mean that workplace stress is not a hazard or that it is the product of a worker's imagination.

People spend more and more time at work, therefore the leaders of organizations should identify and prevent stress among employees. Today's working environment is very cold and demanding in economical and psychological context. People are emotionally, physically and spiritually exhausted. There is less and less joy within success among people. In organizations the increasing trend of reducing the number of employees means more work for the employed at each workplace. On the other hand, there is more and more bureaucracy, which also produces a bigger extent of work. Because someone must do all this work, an employee, who is responsible for it, is more and more subjected to stress, which he or she is not even aware of until he/she is seriously ill. These people often think that these are only temporary problems which can be removed with a short rest, but they are wrong. The most frequent consequences are psychical, where the individual loses his intellectual ability to work. It is worth mentioning the stress that lasts a long time (several years) with short breaks. That means that human never think freely without the burden and resistance, or the problem that always occurs around him/her (Ivanko and Stare 2007).

Foster (2002), a professional speaker on stress management, surveyed mid-level managers and found stress to be a major determinant in worker productivity. According to the study, the primary areas affected by stress are employee morale, absenteeism, and decision-making abilities. By recognizing that a problem exists and by addressing the issue, managers can reduce stressful activities and increase worker performance in the business organization.

Harrold and Wayland (2002) reported that increasing stress affects morale, productivity, organizational efficiency, absenteeism, and profitability for both individuals and the organization. The problem for businesses today is knowing how to determine stressful areas in their organizations and how to use constructive confrontation methods to reduce stress and improve efficiency. According to the authors, organizations that make a positive effort to deal with stress not only help build trust among their employees, but also increase the productivity of their employees and the organization as well.

Maurer (2002) stated that stress-induced illnesses are prevalent in the workplace today, and stress is the problem of the sufferer and the employer. Stress causes absenteeism and can lead to other problems such as drug addiction, alcoholism, depression, and poor job performance. According the Maurer, the annual Barlow

Corporation Forum on Human Resource Issues and Trends reported that large numbers of companies noticed severe levels of stress exhibited by employees. The forum's panelists agreed that more needed to be done in the workplace to help employees manage stress. Some of the suggestions were to expand wellness programs, offer stress-management seminars and teach staff how to balance work and family life. Maurer also noted the Olympic TeamTech, a computer management company, has dealt with employee stress by providing training programs, monitoring employee concerns, and meeting once a month to be proactive instead of reactive. Olympic TeamTech's turnover is less than the industry average.

Schorr (2001), a stress-management consultant, stated that stress causes problems in the workplace which negatively affect employee health and organizational productivity. Stress can lead to problems such as job dissatisfaction, alcoholism, absenteeism, physical ailments, and poor job performance. If managers know how to prevent and cope with stress, productivity can be increased. Many companies instituted stress-management programs that led to a decline in absenteeism, a decrease in sickness and accident costs, and/or an increase in job performance. Schorr reported that a stress inventory, available from a stress-management program, can assist executives and managers in assessing employee stress. The inventory can identify the sources of stress, which may include physical elements as well as other factors. Once these sources have been assessed, the program can provide the necessary skills for coping with the problems, and participants can learn that there are alternative ways of reacting to stress.

It happens that managers often do not cope with the stress of their employees. They are afraid that if they acknowledge the stress in the workplace, employees will demand reduction of their workloads, better working conditions among others. They believe that stress does not belong among the obligations of employers, nor are sure that the anti-stress action, even if they have money, time and knowledge will bring them success. In the case of the problem of an individual, the solution is in his/her hands. The organization does not see how stress can affect the actual success of the organization, so the fact that individual employees are suffering from stress in the workplace is not a cause for alarm for the organization. However, stress in the workplace can cause huge financial losses and reduce profitability. Stress is therefore a problem of the organization as a whole and not just of an individual (Ivanko and Stare, 2007) hence required mitigation should be put in to help different organizations and individuals handle stress. Andrew (2001) suggests that stress management is about developing new perspectives in our lives and learning time management techniques. To help manage some of the stress generated from an unbalanced work life, there is the need to consider delegating some of one's extra

work activities. In the alternative, work load could be addressed with employers by explaining the need for assistance with some tasks. These could serve as ways of creating a positive work-life balance which will help manage stress eventually.

Stress is personal in that stress affects individuals in different ways. In similar situations or conditions some people cope, even thrive, on the pressure, whilst others find it difficult to cope and suffer negative stress as a result. It is also personal in the sense that the amount of control that an individual has, over their work conditions, events, and work-life balance, will influence the amount of negative stress that they suffer from. Those individuals with greater control will tolerate and manage stress levels, or avoid them altogether, more successfully (Williams, 2000). Not all stress is harmful. In fact some stress is not only desirable but essential to life. Research has demonstrated that within certain limits, an individual's performance actually improves with increased level of stress. For example, an athlete is able to run faster under the stress of competition. A student studying for examinations is able to think quicker and stay alert because of the stress of impending examinations. Stress brings out the best potential in all of us. It helps us to be creative and gives us enthusiasm in what we do (Lim and Choon, 2002).

Also, Cartwright and Cooper (2002) developed a model which includes occupational stressors, strain (ill-health) and organizational commitment. Seven occupational stressors are distinguished, namely, work relationships (i.e. poor or unsupportive relationships with colleagues and/or superiors, isolation and unfair treatment), work-life imbalance (such as; when work interferes with the personal and home life of individuals), overload (such as; unmanageable workloads and time pressures), job security (such as; fear of job loss or obsolescence), control (such as; lack of influence in the way work is organized and performed), resources and communication (such as having the appropriate training, equipment and resources), pay and benefits (such as; the financial rewards that work brings) and aspects of the job are sources of stress. Commitment refers to an effect of stress. Poor health is an outcome of stress, which can be used to ascertain if workplace pressures have positive and motivating or negative and damaging effects.

However, poor health may not necessarily be indicative of workplace stress. Individuals may, for example, be unwell because they choose not to lead a healthy lifestyle or may be unaware of how to do so (Jackson & Rothmann, 2006). Meanwhile, Burke (1988 in Lu et al., 2003) grouped job stressors into the following six categories: physical environment, role stressors, organizational structure and job characteristics, relationships with others, career development, and work-family conflict, while Copper *et al.* (1988 in Lu et al., 2003) identified six sources of stress at work: factors intrinsic to the job, management role, relationship with

others, career and achievement, organizational structure and climate, and home/work interface.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research design

The study employed survey design. Survey design is perceived to be authoritative by people in general and it is easily understood and can therefore result in valuable findings if correct procedures are followed (Patton, 2002).

Target population

The target population for this study was employees in the Faculty of commerce and Health science in Kisii University. There are 150 employees in the Faculty of commerce and Health science in the Kisii University. The target population is the population to which the researcher used to generalize the results of the study. Target population is an experimentally accessible population, sometimes referred to as a survey population (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003).

Sampling procedure

Purposive, convenient and simple random sampling were used. Purposive sampling was used to select the study area and convenient sampling was used to select the faculties to participate in the study. Simple random sampling was used to select individual cases to participate in the study.

Data collection instrument

For this study, questionnaires were used to collect data. The questionnaires were structured using the Likert scale format with a five-point response scale. In this Likert scale type of questionnaires, the respondents are given five response choices (Kothari, 2008).

Validity and reliability of research instruments

According to Patton (2002) validity is the extent to which an instrument asks the right questions in terms of accuracy. Validity is the degree to which the results obtained from the analysis of the data actually represent the phenomenon under study (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). Pre-testing was done to test the validity of the research instruments. The researcher pre-tested the questionnaire on 10 respondents in Faculty of Education. These respondents as well as their answers were not

part of the actual study process and were only used for testing purposes. The reliability of the research instruments will be measured using the Cronbach Coefficient Alpha (α). A reliability coefficient of 0.7 or over was assumed to reflect the internal reliability of the instruments (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2000).

Data analysis

The quantitative research method was used to analyze the data. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics were presented in form of frequency distributions and percentages. Inferential statistics (Multiple regression and Pearson correlation) were used to test the hypotheses. Pearson product correlation coefficients (r) can take on value from -1 to +1. The sign out of this indicates whether there is a positive correlation (as one variable increase so too does the other) or a negative correlation (as one variable increases, the other decreases).

Pearson product moment was used to test the following hypotheses: H_01 there is no significant relation between causes of stress and employee performance. H_02 there is no significant relationship between consequences of stress and employee performance. H_03 there is no significant relationship between stress coping strategies and employee performance. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2001) multiple regression tells how well a set of variables is able to predict a particular outcome. A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine whether a group of independent variables (causes and consequences of stress were the best predictors of dependent variable. The R and R^2 , were got from running linear multiple regression. The R was run to gauge how well the model predicts the observed data. The R^2 was run to determine the amount of variation in the outcome variable that is accounted for by the model or it indicated how all the predictors in the model accounted for dependent variable (employee performance). The adjusted R^2 was run to give the idea of how well the model generalizes and ideally, its value would be the same or close to R^2 (.652).

Multiple Regression model

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Y = Employee performance (dependent variable)

X_1 = consequences of stress

X_2 = Causes of stress

X_3 = Stress coping strategies

β_0 = is the constant or intercept

β_{1-n} = are the regression coefficients or change induced in Y by each X

ε = is the error term or stochastic term

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Personal characteristics of the respondents

The age of the respondents indicated that most employees in the organization were between 20-29 years (42.2%) of the respondents, followed by between 30-39 years (12.3%) of the respondents and finally over 40 years with the lowest number of employees in the organization contributing to 11.8% of the respondents. This implies that majority of employees are young with inadequate experience and this cannot effectively contribute to the operation goals. They also take the advantage of being young and they feel still have great chance of advancing and getting another or a better job. Generally, younger employees tend to be more ambitious and career-oriented and hence, they prefer challenging jobs, moving from one career to the other.

The gender results of the respondents showed that there was gender imbalance within the organizations where 61.5% were male and 38.5% female. This indicates that gender has a role in influencing career choice. This also shows that Faculty of Commerce and Health science have got a large number of male employees than female in relation to the Kenyan perspective where there is fight for equality. It therefore follows that the equation is still far from balancing and thus women need to strive to train in areas which could be believed to belong to men and the same to women to be able to reach to a balance.

The marital status of the respondents indicated that most employees were married (33.2%), followed by single (29.4%), divorced (19.8%), separated (12.8%) and the lowest respondents being widowed with (4.8%). Considering that most married people have other family responsibilities then this could affect their performance negatively. It could be also speculated that the non-married staff are willing to spend more of their time on developing their career, and in turn demand better treatment from management and seeking for better place to work. On the other hand the married employees are more inclined to strike a balance between work and family life. Hence, job related performance is comparatively important to them.

It is evident from the study that most employees (37.4%) in the organization only had up to masters level of education, followed by (21.9%) tertiary level of education and minority of the respondents (19.8%) doctorate education level. This implies that most of employees in Kisii University are literate and innovative hence can be able to work towards the expected output of the institution. In general; employees tend to be more demanding if they are literate and better informed hence tend to strike a balance between the level of outcome and payment.

Table 1. Correlation analysis results

		Employee Performance	Causes of Stress	Consequences of stress	Coping Strategies
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.600	.429	.634
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.002	.001	.001
Cause of Stress	Pearson Correlation	.600	1	.152	.382
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.002		.478	.065
Consequences of stress	Pearson Correlation	.429	.152	1	.747
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.001	.478		.000
Coping Strategies	Pearson Correlation	.634	.382	.747	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.001	.065	.000	

Source: Survey Data, 2013

Table 2. Model summary for regression analysis of survey data

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.102	.268		.381	.000		
	X1	.618	.242	.423	2.552	.001	.813	1.229
	X2	.018	.151	.028	.119	.002	.420	2.379
	X3	.383	.209	.452	1.829	.002	.367	2.722

INFERENCE STATISTICS

Correlation analysis

The Pearson correlation was performed to determine the relationship between stress and employee performance. The Pearson correlation was used to test the relationship between employee performance (Y) and causes of stress (X_1), consequences of stress (X_2), strategies of as shown in table 1 above. The employee performance had a positive relationship to the causes of stress at 5% level of significance. The causes of stress positively correlated to the employee's performance $r = .429$, $P < .01$ (2 - tailed) at 1% level of significance. The consequences of stress positively correlated to the employee's performance $r = .429$, $P < .01$ (2 - tailed) at 1% level of significance. The stress coping strategies positively correlated to the employee's performance $r = .634$, $P < .01$ (2 - tailed) at 1% level of significance.

Regression Analysis Results

Model summary for regression analysis of survey data

R^2 represented the measure of variability in employee's performance that is accounted for by the predictors

(independent variables). From the model, ($R^2 = .652$) an indication that all the predictors in the model account for 65.2% variation in enhancing employee's performance. This shows that variation in employee's performance has been explained well by the predictors in the model. The adjusted R^2 gives the idea of how well our model generalizes and ideally, its value would be the same or very close to R^2 . In our case the value of adjusted R^2 is .625, showing that, if the model was derived from the population rather than the sample it would account for approximately 62.5% less variance in employee's performance. The change statistics were used to test whether the change in R^2 is significant using F- ratio. The model caused R^2 to change from zero to .652 and this change gave rise to an F- ratio of 8.224, which is significant at a probability less than .05.

The analysis of variance was used to test whether the model could significantly fit in predicting the outcome than using the mean. The F- ratio represents the ratio of improvement in prediction that results from fitting the model, relative to the inaccuracy that exists in the model. The F- ratio was 8.224 which is likely to happen by chance and was significant ($P < 0.05$).

The model significantly improved the ability to predict the factors enhancing employee performance. The study found a significant regression equation $F = (8.224, p < 0.001)$. This shows that there was a linear relationship between the employee performance and the predictors

Table 3. Regression Coefficients Results for the survey data

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		
					R Square Change	F Change	Sig. F Change
1	.743 ^a	.652	.625	.14647	.652	8.224	.001

(causes of stress, consequences of stress and stress coping strategies) in the population.

Regression coefficients results for the survey data

The β value tells us about the relationship between the employees performance with each predictor. The positive β values indicate the positive relationship between the predictors and the outcome whereas a negative coefficient represents a negative relationship. The t test was used as a measure to identify whether the predictors were making a significant contribution to the model. When the t-test associated with β -values is significant then, the predictor is making a significant contribution to the model. The smaller the value of significance (the larger the value of t) i.e. greater is the contributor of that predictor. This study found that causes of stress, consequences of stress and stress coping strategies were significant predictors of employee performance. The constant and the β coefficients were used to create the estimated prediction (regression) equation, which for this model is as follows:

$$\hat{Y} = 1.102 + 0.618X_1 + 0.018X_2 + 0.383X_3$$

The positive β values indicate the positive relationship between the predictors and the outcome, whereas a negative coefficient represents a negative relationship. From the above model, we can note that there existed a positive relationship between \hat{Y} (employee performance) and the three independent variables (causes of stress, consequences of stress and stress coping strategies) based on the positive coefficients of the variables; $\beta_1 = .618$, $\beta_2 = .018$, $\beta_3 = .383$. It showed that when the causes of stress changes by one unit percent, employee performance changes by 61.8.1% and when the consequences of stress changes by one unit percent, employee performance changes by 1.8% and stress coping strategies changes by one unit percent, employee performance changes by 38.3%. From the model the predictor of employees performance were found to be significantly positive Causes of stress ($t = 2.552$, $P < 0.05$), Consequences of stress ($t = 0.119$, $P < 0.05$) and Stress coping strategies ($t = 1.829$, $P < 0.05$).

To test the Collinearity in the data tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) were used (Table 3 above). The model has VIF values that are below and above 10 and tolerance statistics are also below and above .2. Therefore we can conclude that there is no

Collinearity in our data, with VIF values below 10 and tolerance statistics above 0.2. Tests were also run for multi-collinearity using the adjusted R^2 and the overall adjusted R^2 and it showed that the adjusted R^2 values did not exceed the overall adjusted R^2 valued of .652. The values of the two tests are equal an indication that there is no multi-Collinearity among the regressors. Multi-collinearity is said to exist when the adjusted R^2 value is greater than the overall adjusted R^2 value.

DISCUSSION

The first hypothesis, which states that, there is no significant relationship between causes of stress and employee performance, was rejected. This shows that causes of stress and employee performance are positively and significantly correlated ($r = .429$, $P < .01$) (2 - tailed) at 1% level of significance. This finding is inline with Ismail & Hong (2011) who states that stress is a cause of dissatisfaction among the employees like role conflicts, work intensification, relationship with colleagues and unfavorable working conditions are the major factors of creating stress. It also agrees with Shahid (2012) who states that inflexible work hours, work over load, risky job and poor coworker relations are the main contributor to job stress, which create dissatisfaction among the employees.

The second hypothesis, which states that, there is no significant relationship between consequences of stress and employee performance, was rejected. This shows that work related stress and employee performance is positively and significantly correlated $r = .429$, $P < .01$ (2 - tailed) at 1% level of significance. This finding is inline with Kivimaki *et al.* (2002) who emphasized that work-related stress has been associated with a number of ill-health problems. Outcomes of work-related stress are: Physical problems; Mental health problems; Reduction in quality of output; Reduction in quality of productivity; indolence; absenteeism; presenteeism. This is a situation where the worker is present at work, but the worker feels too ill to be able to work effectively and efficiently (Jayashree, 2010). Casio (2013) Stress has its' outcomes on the organization and the employees too; on the organizational side considered job stress and its' consequences as major factors in increasing organizations' cost; as a result of absenteeism, work stoppage, turnovers, accidents and strikes. Jaramillo *et*

a/. (2011) and it has a direct impact on the communication process inside the organization and the interaction with customers, in maintaining good and balanced relationships with peers and leaders.

The third hypothesis, which states that, there is no significant relationship between stress coping strategies and employee performance, was rejected. The stress coping strategies positively correlated to the employee's performance ($r = .634$, $P < .01$) (2 - tailed) at 1% level of significance. This finding is inline with Synder (2001) who states that, "coping reflects thinking, feeling, or acting so as to preserve a satisfied psychological state when it is threatened. Coping is typically not a single response, but a series of responses, initiated and repeated as necessary to handling the remaining, continuing, or transformed nature of the stressor."

CONCLUSION

Work related stress, causes of stress and stress coping strategies have effect on employee performance. The main observation drawn from this study is that although stressors will almost certainly have negative impact on one's mind/psychology (such as poor concentration, absenteeism, frustrations, poor organization and decision making, less active in problem solving) which consequently affect job performance.

The use of health coping strategies-psychotherapy (psychoanalysis/talk therapy- with supervisors & colleagues, having time for physical activity during work hours, involving employees on decision making, increase career developments, appraisal of the work done through timely payment of work overload) can help employees adapt to challenging stressors and maintain high level of performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Universities should provide facilities and times for physical activities for their staffs/its employees. There is need for Faculty heads/supervisors to create time to share with their staffs as far as work activities and assignments are concern. There need for university management to identify suitable stress coping strategies to help reduce stress employee work place stress. There is need to encourage the use of talk therapy strategies to reduce stress and improve job performance. This can be done by sharing work challenges with supervisors and colleagues.

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